

Improvement of accent classification models through Grad-Transfer from Spectrograms and Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping

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Abstract—Automatic accent classification is an active research field concerning speech processing. It can be useful to identify a speaker’s region of origin, which can be applied in police investigations carried out by Law Enforcement Agencies, as well as for the improvement of current speech recognition systems. This paper presents a novel descriptor called Grad-Transfer, extracted using the Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) method based on convolutional neural network (CNN) interpretability. Additionally, we propose a methodology for accent classification that implements Grad-Transfer, which is based on transferring the knowledge acquired by a CNN to other machine learning algorithms. The paper works on two hypotheses: the coarse localization maps produced by Grad-CAM on spectrograms are able to highlight the regions of the spectrograms that are important for predicting accents, and Grad-Transfer descriptors computed from audios represent distinctive descriptions of the target accents. These hypotheses were demonstrated experimentally, clustering the generated Grad-Transfer descriptors according to the original accent of the audios using Birch and k -means algorithms. We carried out experiments on the VCTK dataset, seeing an increase of accuracy in the results obtained by a Naive Bayes Gaussian classifier up to 7.46%, compared to a model trained with spectrograms. This demonstrates that Grad-Transfer is able to improve the performance of accent classification models and opens the door to new implementations in similar tasks.

Index Terms—Accent classification, Grad-CAM, Grad-Transfer, speech processing

I. INTRODUCTION

THE human voice provides valuable information about who generates it, which can potentially be used in a wide variety of tasks [1], [2], [3]. The particular accent of each individual provides some of this information. An accent is a particular form of pronunciation that can be associated with the locality in which the speaker resides or has resided, his ethnic group, the influence of his first language, or even his socioeconomic status [4]. The ability to correctly identify the accent can enable a system to obtain relevant information about a person, solely through recordings of their voice [5].

The automatic classification of accents is a field of research focused on the creation of automatic systems capable of identifying the accent of different speakers [3]. In addition to its usefulness as a method for characterizing speaker traits, it has potential in a variety of fields, such as its application in improving current Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems [6], [7]. In general, the accent is one of the most important factors influencing the performance of ASR systems,

along with gender [8], [9]. Previous research has shown that the accent is one of the biggest problems in creating variation-resistant ASR systems [10].

Additionally, accent classification systems by themselves can be useful for some organizations, such as Law Enforcement Agencies, providing hints about the identity of suspects by identifying their place of origin based on their accent.

Researchers in the field of accent classification have used different classical machine learning algorithms (MLA), such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) [11], Hidden Markov Models (HMM) [12], Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) [13]; and also Deep Learning algorithms, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [14] and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) [3]. And even, combinations between several of these algorithms [15].

Spectrograms are commonly used in speech processing tasks [6], because they are detailed graphical representations of audio. The use of spectrograms allows problems in the field of speech processing to be addressed by models frequently used in image classification, for example, CNNs, which are widely used in spectrogram processing [16], [14].

The majority of the recent research works are based on the use of CNNs [6], [17], due to their high modeling capabilities. The present paper seeks to take advantage of these characteristics and use them to improve the performance of classical models through the creation of a new hybrid method.

The results obtained by CNNs can be interpreted by methods such as Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) [18], which are useful to extract, in a weighted way, the most representative inputs of each possible result obtained by the CNNs. Grad-CAM is a class-discriminative localization technique that allows extracting information about the knowledge that a CNN has acquired during the training process. In this work, a knowledge gap in the potential utility of Grad-CAM and similar techniques is identified.

In the present paper, the performance of popular CNNs architectures and multiple machine learning algorithms (MLA) is evaluated for native English accent classification. Furthermore, Grad-CAM is used as a method to create feature vectors that retain the knowledge derived from CNNs rather than as a tool to create visual explanations. This new information can be used in combination with spectrograms to provide more distinctive feature vectors that may increase the performance obtained with classical models.

We present a method to classify different accents from audio

files by using the information from spectrograms and Grad-CAMs. Having as a novelty the use of Grad-CAM as a feature extractor and intermediate representation allows to transfer of knowledge from a CNN to an MLA, instead of its “common” use as a model interpretability method.

Furthermore, we present Grad-Transfer, a novel descriptor based on the concatenation of a flattened spectrogram and the dimensionality-reduced heatmaps of the Grad-CAMs. This descriptor takes advantage of the knowledge extracted by a CNN to be used as additional information to improve the distinctiveness of an audio descriptor, and thus achieve higher performance with MLA classifiers. The presented descriptor is especially useful in situations where a classical MLA yields better performance than CNN models, allowing to boost the performance of the MLA even further. This is the case of the use presented in this paper, which is focused on the classification of native English accents.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that Grad-CAM is implemented as a method to transfer knowledge from a machine learning model to another one, as well as a feature extractor, in the audio processing field.

The main contributions of this work are:

- The introduction of novel Grad-Transfer feature extractors for representing distinctive audio characteristics that combines information from the CNN-based class-discriminative localization technique Grad-CAM and from spectrograms.
- A method for accent classification that uses the proposed features, so that the method transfers knowledge from CNNs to MLA.
- A publicly available set-up of the VCTK dataset for accent classification that can be used by researchers to test their methods and compare the results to this work.

We validate the effectiveness of the proposed Grad-Transfer feature vectors by carrying out experiments on the VCTK dataset, outperforming the baseline methods.

The remaining part of the document is organized as follows: in Section II, a review of state of the art in the field of accent classification is presented. Then, in Section III, the proposed method is explained, and Grad-Transfer is introduced as a tool to increase the performance of classical algorithms. In Section IV, the dataset used is described, and the experimental setup is presented, which includes the preliminary results obtained using classical MLA and CNNs that led to the creation of the final experimental setup. Section V shows the results and the discussion of the work, and Section VI draws the conclusions of this paper.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The approaches used in the automatic identification of accents are similar to those used in language identification. They can be grouped into approaches using *acoustic modeling* and approaches using *phonotactic modeling* [19]. Acoustic modeling focuses on the spectral characteristics of sound waves, while phonotactic modeling does on phoneme recognition and subsequent analysis.

A. Phonotactic Modeling

All languages spoken by humans are composed of sets of phonemes, which are basic theoretical units representing the minimum articulation of a vowel or a consonantal sound and which are postulated to study spoken human language [20].

Phonotactic modeling is characterized by classifying the accent of an audio signal by processing its phonetic transcription, which is obtained through *phoneme recognizers* [19]. A phoneme recognizer transcribes the voice into a sequence of known phonemes.

The phoneme recognizer produces phonetic sequences that are used to feed systems called language models (LMs), which are in charge of estimating a probability distribution model for each accent. LMs are models that assign probabilities to a sequence of words, such as the probability of a word appearing in a sentence given the previous set of words. Also, an LM can determine the probability that an n-gram (sequence of n words) belongs to a previously analyzed set of n-grams, which could represent a given accent.

Most phonotactic modeling methods are based on statistical language models, which are LMs that use traditional statistical techniques and linguistic rules to learn the probability distribution of words [21].

Among the methods that have used phonotactic modeling, we have the work of Kumpf et al. [22] in which it is used an accent-dependent parallel phoneme recognizer to classify native Australian English speakers and foreign-accented speakers whose mother languages are Levantine Arabic and South Vietnamese. The accuracies achieved are 85.3% and 76.6% for the classification of two and three accents, respectively.

Angkititrakul et al. [23] implemented an accent classification system based on stochastic and parametric trajectory models using an accent-sensitive word corpus. The corpus contained five English speaker groups with native American English and English spoken with Mandarin Chinese, French, Thai and Turkish accents. This system achieved an accent classification accuracy of 90%.

Similar approaches have been used for language classification, such as [24], in which they train a statistical phonotactic model to classify the Indonesian languages Minangkabau, Sundanese, and Javanese. Using phone recognition followed by language modeling and parallel phone recognition followed by language modeling they achieve an accuracy of 77.4% and 75.94% respectively.

Although phonotactic modeling has been used in multiple investigations, advances in deep learning have made speech processing research focus mostly on acoustic modeling.

B. Acoustic Modeling

Acoustic modeling is based on the processing of the original audio wave or its spectral characteristics. One of the ways to work with spectral characteristics of audio is through embeddings, which are representations capable of expressing statements with a variable number of observations as a single vector that retains most of the statement variations. There are several types of embeddings, such as i-vectors and x-vectors.

Both have been widely used in audio classification tasks [1], [25], [26], [27].

The use of classification systems based on the attributes modeled by i-vectors has shown to be able to achieve superior results to those obtained by phonotactic modeling, in tasks such as language recognition [28]. A small set of speech attributes is sufficient for a complete characterization of spoken languages. Robust universal speech attribute detectors can be designed by sharing data between different languages, as shown by Siniscalchi et al. [29].

Behravan et al. [30] used i-vectors to define a common set of “universal” fundamental units that describe the manner and place of articulation as attributes of speech in all evaluated spoken accents. They evaluated the method on two datasets, the first dataset contains one native English group and another 7 groups of English speakers with a foreign accent, and the second dataset comprehends 7 groups of non-native speakers. They obtained a 15% and 8% improvement over the result achieved with an approach based on Siniscalchi’s et al. work [29].

Due to the improvement of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) in recent years, a new type of embeddings has become popular, which are generated by extracting the outputs of a hidden layer of a pre-trained DNN. Therefore, it takes advantage of the modeling capabilities of a network trained with a large amount of data and reusing it with a small dataset.

A specific type of these embeddings are the x-vectors, which require the application of a Probabilistic Linear Discriminant Analysis (PLDA) after the generation of the embeddings for their processing, in which it can be determined which x-vectors are the most similar to each other, and with that, determine the category of new x-vectors.

X-vectors have been used in related tasks, Wang S. et al. [1] uses x-vectors for speaker verification, with Tagalog and Cantonese languages, from the NIST SRE 2004-2010 datasets, achieving an improvement in the equal error rate of 15.4% and 34.7% respectively, when comparing the results of x-vectors with respect to the results with i-vectors.

Linjia Sun [2] used x-vectors for language classification, with the NIST LRE07 dataset containing 14 languages and the Arabic dialect identification dataset containing 17 dialects, achieving an improvement of up to 10.5% and 9.8% respectively, when comparing x-vectors accuracy with i-vectors accuracy.

The most recent models based on embeddings generation do not require the use of PLDA, but the comparison of embeddings is done by means of cosine similarity calculation. Among these models we can find Wav2Vec2 [31], a model created for speech to text conversion; XLSR-Wav2Vec2 [32], created from Wav2Vec2 but finetuned to work with multiple languages; HuBERT [33], a self-supervised approach for embedding generation based on BERT; and WavLM [34], based on HuBERT but with optimized architecture and focused on its usefulness in speech to text conversion tasks, as well as non-speech to text tasks.

A way to represent the spectral characteristics of audio is through the use of spectrograms, which can be used as inputs for machine learning models. Multiple investigations

have used spectrograms as a representation of audio [35]. A spectrogram is a result of calculating in frames the spectrum of a signal divided into windows; the result is a matrix containing information about the time, frequency, and energy of each instant (represented by color). Among the classic machine learning models that used end-to-end systems approaches fed by spectrograms are SVM, HMM, and GMM [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]. Tang et al. [41] made a comparison in accent detection between SVM and HNN, concluding that both approaches obtain similar performances and a similar speed of convergence.

The recent developments in the field of deep learning, have caused that the new advances, produced in the automatic classification of accents, are focused on the use of models like DNN, RNN, and CNN, as well as, in the fusion of these models with classic algorithms like SVM [42], [6], [14], [15]. Jiao, et al. [3] studied the combination of traditional and deep learning approaches for the task of automatic accent classification, using different combinations of models to classify 11 accents, and measuring the error level by means of unweighted average recall (UAR). Among the results presented, SVM obtained a 45.1% UAR, a model that merges DNN+RNN achieved a 52.2% UAR and a model that merges DNN+RNN+SVM yielded a 55.8% UAR.

With the evolution of CNNs and RNNs, multiple investigations in audio processing have focused on taking advantage of the representative capacity of CNNs, with the ability to model temporal features of RNNs [15]. In related fields, such as language identification, architectures that combine CNN with RNN have been used, as is the case of the work of Bartz et al. [43], where an architecture called CRNN is proposed, specifically designed for learning from spectrograms. Later, Singh et al. [17] applied CRNN and CNN to the automatic classification of accents, achieving an accuracy with CRNN 4.73% higher than that achieved with a CNN.

Another research where a CNN was used for accent classification is the work of Zeng et al. [6], where a modified ResNet architecture was presented and applied in the multi-label classification of accents and speakers. With the purpose of accent classification, they achieved 89.67% accuracy on the VCTK dataset. This work combines the task of speaker classification and accent classification in the same model, so they do not separate the test and train set speakers. Our work focuses specifically on accent classification so in our case the train and test sets contain different speakers, so we cannot compare our results with their results.

Most of the previous research focuses on the classification of foreign accents in English speakers. However, this paper focuses only on the classification of native English speaker accents to address the needs of LEAs. The fact that the speakers are native English speakers increases the complexity of the task due to the acoustic similarities among the groups to be classified.

Grad-CAM is a technique that weighs data according to the relevance they have in the training process of a neural network. It is very popular in fields where it is necessary to have certainty about the reasons for the decisions made by machine learning models, such as, for example, the medical

field, where it has been widely used since it allows the interpretability of the generated models and the consequent search for explanations for their outputs [44], [45], [46], [47]. As far as we know, there is no work using Grad-CAM to extract features from the knowledge learned by a CNN, and use it to improve the performance of another machine learning model [18], [48], [49], [50]. In this paper, such features are used to enhance the performance of accent classification systems fed by spectrograms.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Grad-Transfer feature descriptor

The proposed Grad-Transfer descriptor is constructed from the information contained in the heatmaps generated by a convolutional network through a CNN interpretability method. A model interpretability method produces a visualization of the CNN predictions by highlighting important regions in the image for predicting a target concept. They are represented as heatmaps that highlight the pixels that have the greatest impact on the prediction score with different levels of intensity values [18].

Among the available interpretability methods are Grad-CAM [18], Occlusion Sensitivity [51], SmoothGrad [52], Vanilla Gradient [53], and Integrated Gradients [54]. Examples of the results of applying each interpretability method to the same spectrogram, and using “American” as the predicted class, are presented in Fig. 1.

In the present paper, Grad-CAM is used as a method of interpretability, which was selected after a visual comparison of the five interpretability methods analyzed on some audio files. Grad-CAM is a highly class-discriminative method that highlights different parts of a spectrogram depending on a target class.

Grad-CAM extracts the gradient information from a layer (usually the final layer) of a convolutional network and uses it to highlight the probable regions responsible for an event, such as the prediction of a certain category. In principle, Grad-CAM takes the final map of convolutional features and then weighs each channel in that feature with the gradient of the class with respect to the channel. That is, it determines the intensity with which the input image activates different channels, according to the relevance of each channel with respect to the class.

Let the spatial score of a specific class S_c be the global average pooling in two dimensions i and j for the gradient of the respective output class y^c concerning the features map A_{ij}^k . We multiply the resulting value with the features map along its channel axis k . Then we apply average pooling to the result on the channel dimension k . The result is the spatial score map of size $i \times j$.

$$S^c = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k \frac{\partial y^c}{\partial A_{ij}^k} A_{ij}^k, \quad (1)$$

where, \sum represents the average pooling operation and Z is the number of pixels in the feature map.

The generated heatmaps are element-wise multiplied with the original spectrogram to obtain a new spectrogram in which the regions in the spectrogram predicted as a target class

Fig. 1. Element-wise multiplication of the produced heatmap and the original spectrogram (a), by different methods of interpretability (b-f) applied to the same audio on the VCTK dataset, through a Densenet CNN pre-trained for accent recognition. Heatmaps were generated using “American” as the predicted class.

present higher intensity values, henceforth named a Grad-CAM spectrogram.

To condense the most relevant information contained in the resulting Grad-CAM spectrograms, we apply Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [55]. Through a PCA each Grad-CAM spectrogram is summarized into a low dimensional vector that retains only the most representative features of the Grad-CAM spectrogram while discarding the remaining information.

We empirically determined the number of principal components that retain a sufficient proportion of the total variance. For this, we took a subset of 10124 audio files from the VCTK dataset and computed the Grad-CAM spectrograms of each audio. Then, PCA was applied to all Grad-CAM spectrograms converting them into vectors of 10000 principal components (PC) each. Then, the variance of the PCs of all the vectors is calculated, so the result is a single vector of 10000 elements, where each element represents the variance of the PCs in the same position. All the variances are added together and divided by each element of the variance vector, obtaining the proportion of the total variance that each element represents. Finally, all the values are organized from highest to lowest, and they are added from left to right to obtain the accumulated

TABLE I
THE NUMBER OF PRINCIPAL COMPONENTS THAT ARE NEEDED TO EXPLAIN MULTIPLE CUMULATIVE VARIANCE VALUES.

Cumulative variance	Required PCs
0.999	3503
0.995	693
0.990	257
0.950	37
0.900	23
0.800	18

proportion, in this way it is possible to know how many PCs are necessary to obtain a determined proportion of the total variance, as it can be observed in the Table I.

In this paper, we empirically selected a 95% of the variance to represent the data, so all the Grad-CAM spectrograms were converted to 37 principal components. If we apply the inverse process of PCA to reconstruct the original images from the PCs, we obtain images that, as can be seen in Fig. 2, store only the most relevant information representing the highest variance in the original images. It can be seen that for a variance of 95%, the converted Grad-CAM spectrogram is able to preserve the highlight of the important region while discarding a detailed representation of the information.

We define a Grad-Transfer feature descriptor as the concatenation of the principal components of all the Grad-CAM spectrograms obtained for each targeted class.

B. Evaluating Grad-CAM spectrograms as a method of knowledge representation of models

We consider the following hypothesis about Grad-Transfer: the coarse localization maps produced by Grad-CAM on spectrograms may highlight the regions of the spectrograms –frequencies and times of the audio– that are important for predicting a target class –accent–. This hypothesis is based on the fact that, since the spectrograms are represented in the frequency and time axes [18], the position of each element in them is relevant. Thus, a second hypothesis is that Grad-Transfer feature descriptors computed from audios present distinctive descriptions of the target accents.

To test the mentioned hypotheses, we proposed an experiment in which, using clustering algorithms, it is verified that the generated Grad-Transfer descriptors are clustered according to their corresponding class.

Clustering was applied to Grad-Transfer descriptors obtained from the audios used for training the CNN. The results of clustering using the *k*-means [56] algorithm and Birch [57] algorithm are presented in Table II. The values shown correspond to the rate of examples of each accent among all the examples assigned to each of the clusters. In both cases, the number of clusters to be generated was predetermined at five.

As it can be seen, most clusters have a distinctive majority accent. Let us suppose that all the examples clustered in a cluster have the majority accent of that cluster. In that case, we can calculate accuracy by comparing the real label with that of the majority accent of its assigned cluster. The accuracy

TABLE II
RATE OF GRAD-TRANSFER DESCRIPTORS THAT ARE CLUSTERED AS THE GIVEN ACCENTS IN EACH CLUSTER GENERATED BY K-MEANS AND BIRCH ALGORITHMS.

Accent	Clusters				
	0	1	2	3	4
<i>k</i> -means					
Irish	0.293	0.006	0.121	0.059	0.355
Canadian	<u>0.274</u>	0.937	0.001	0.003	0.000
American	0.005	0.022	0.828	0.260	0.078
Scottish	0.231	0.022	0.013	0.429	0.248
British	0.197	0.013	0.037	0.249	<u>0.319</u>
Birch					
Irish	0.358	0.000	0.009	0.053	0.364
Canadian	0.051	0.978	0.004	0.294	0.012
American	0.001	0.002	0.992	0.009	<u>0.363</u>
Scottish	0.347	0.001	0.000	0.378	0.076
British	0.244	0.003	0.011	0.266	0.186

TABLE III
RATE OF ACCURACY IN RELATION TO THE ACTUAL LABEL OF EACH EXAMPLE WITH REGARD TO ITS ASSIGNED CLUSTER.

	Top 1-accuracy	Top 2-accuracy
<i>k</i> -means	0.488	0.717
Birch	0.492	0.759

obtained if we compare the real label with the majority accent (top 1-accuracy) and the accuracy obtained if we compare the real label to the two majority accents (top 2-accuracy) are presented in Table III. The latter measure represents the percentage of examples that were assigned to a cluster where one of the two majority accents corresponds to the real accent.

Given the results obtained, we can conclude that Grad-Transfer feature descriptors, generated from Grad-CAM visualizations, effectively store relevant information that can be categorized according to the original classes (accents) with which a CNN was trained.

C. Pipeline of the methodology

We propose to use Grad-Transfer descriptors as a booster to increase the performance of flattened spectrograms classified by machine learning algorithms. Hence, the final vector, which will be fed to MLA, is composed by the concatenation of the original flattened spectrograms and the Grad-Transfer feature descriptors. Grad-Transfer descriptors are generated from a pre-trained CNN, and by means of them, we transfer part of the knowledge acquired by the CNN to an MLA to improve its performance.

Therefore, as shown in Fig. 3, first we train a CNN that is fed by the original spectrograms to classify a set of accents. Once the CNN is trained, its weights are frozen, and we employ Grad-CAM to generate a heatmap per each considered accent for each spectrogram. The element-wise multiplication of the heatmaps and the spectrograms (Grad-CAM spectrograms) are converted to their 37 PCs, and all the PCs from the same spectrogram are concatenated in a specific order, producing a Grad-Transfer feature descriptor. The considered feature vector is composed by the concatenation of the

Fig. 2. Original and inverse PCA of the Grad-CAM spectrograms for different percentages of stored information considering different numbers of principal components (PC).

flattened spectrogram and the Grad-Transfer descriptor once the values are scaled. Each of the resulting vectors represents an element of the training, validation, or test sets. Finally, the vectors of the training set are used to train an MLA, and its validation is made using the vectors of the validation set. The best of the generated models is evaluated with respect to the test set.

IV. EXPERIMENTATION

A. VCTK Dataset

The Voice Cloning Toolkit (VCTK)¹ is a voice dataset that contains 88328 audio clips from 110 native English speakers with multiple accents, including Australian, Canadian, US, British, Indian, Irish, New Zealand, Northern Irish, Scottish, South African and Welsh. All audios are recorded with a 96 kHz sampling at 24 bits and were recorded by two microphones simultaneously, so the content of each audio is duplicated. Therefore the number of unique clips is reduced to 44164.

A summary of VCTK statistics grouped by speaker and gender is presented in Table IV.

As it can be seen in Table IV, VCTK is highly unbalanced by accents and genders, so in this work, we considered only the five accents that include most of the speakers, i.e. British, American, Scottish, Irish, and Canadian.

On average each speaker has 410 audio clips. The high number of clips per speaker and the small number of speakers, in addition to the existing imbalance in the gender, can cause low performance in the machine learning models. Besides, due to the few speakers per accent, the models may tend to learn the features of each speaker instead of the features of the accents, causing overfitting. These aspects turn the considered set of data into a challenging dataset for accent classification.

TABLE IV
VCTK DATASET STATISTICS BY SPEAKER AND GENDER

Accent	# speakers	Gender	# speakers per gender
British	33	male	15
		female	18
American	22	male	5
		female	17
Scottish	19	male	14
		female	5
Irish	9	male	3
		female	6
Canadian	8	male	3
		female	5
NorthernIrish	6	male	2
		female	4
SouthAfrican	4	male	1
		female	3
Indian	3	male	2
		female	1
Australian	2	male	2
Welsh	1	female	1
NewZealand	1	female	1

B. Experimental setup

1) *Data pre-processing*: For training, the original audios were divided into 4-second-long fragments, without overlapping among fragments.

Based on the hyperparameters used in [58], all the audios were converted to single-channel, 16-bit streams at a 16kHz sampling rate. Then, we used a hamming window of 25 ms width and 10 ms step to produce spectrograms of 512×400 pixels for each 4-second-long audio fragment. To reduce the computational effort required to process the data, the spectrograms were resized to 128×100 pixels, maintaining the original proportions. No other pre-processing of the data was performed, such as removing silences. These spectrograms were subsequently used as the inputs to the models. Examples of the generated spectrograms can be seen in Fig. 4. Since

¹<http://homepages.inf.ed.ac.uk/jyamagis/page3/page58/page58.html>

Fig. 3. Graphic summary of the proposed pipeline. 1) The audios are divided into 4-second sections, each section is interpreted as an independent example and converted to a spectrogram. The generated spectrograms are used to train a CNN model for accent classification. Once trained, the heatmaps of each spectrogram are generated through Grad-CAM and they are element-wise multiplied with the original spectrogram, obtaining what we name Grad-CAM spectrograms. 2) PCA is applied to the Grad-CAM spectrograms and Grad-Transfer feature descriptors are built by the concatenation of principal components of the Grad-CAM spectrograms from each audio. Feature vectors are generated by scaling and concatenating the flatten spectrogram and the Grad-Transfer feature descriptors. 3) An MLA is used for accent classification.

VCTK dataset examples do not share common sentences among speakers, spectrograms in the figure represent different speeches.

2) *Dataset split*: In Table V, the division between the training, validation, and test sets is presented. We considered different speakers for training, validation, and testing to avoid the model implicitly learning to recognize them instead of recognizing accents. From each accent, the speakers with more clips were selected for the creation of this subset. 125 clips with long duration per speaker were included in the test set and another 125 in the validation set, resulting in a total of 250 clips per accent in both partitions. We have made the partition of the dataset publicly available so other researchers can test their methods².

3) *Evaluation Metrics*: Performance is reported in terms of classification accuracy. It is the ratio of the number of correct predictions, N_c , per the total number of input samples, N .

$$Acc = \frac{N_c}{N} \quad (2)$$

The accuracy metric works well with balanced datasets, which is the case of the selected subset extracted from VCTK.

4) *Selection of CNNs and MLAs*: Several of the most popular CNNs architectures and classical MLAs were tested to select the most suitable models to be used in the proposed

Fig. 4. Spectrograms of audio samples of each of the considered accents from the VCTK dataset, which will serve as input to the models presented in this paper. Each spectrogram represents a different speech.

²VCTK dataset partitioning setup: <https://bit.ly/3eGnNT5>

TABLE V
STATISTICS OF THE CONSIDERED SUBSET FROM THE VCTK DATASET FOR TRAINING, VALIDATION, AND TEST

Accent	Gender	Total # of speakers used	Train		Validation		Test	
			# speakers	# clips	# speakers	# clips	# speakers	# clips
British	male	4	2	685	1	125	1	125
	female	4	2	783	1	125	1	125
American	male	1	0	0	0	0	1	125
	female	7	4	1604	2	250	1	125
Scottish	male	4	2	828	1	125	1	125
	female	4	2	848	1	125	1	125
Irish	male	3	2	770	0	0	1	125
	female	5	2	837	2	250	1	125
Canadian	male	3	2	743	0	0	1	125
	female	5	2	784	2	250	1	125

TABLE VI

VALIDATION ACCURACY OF CNN MODELS APPLIED TO THE END-TO-END CLASSIFICATION OF ACCENTS ON A SUBSET OF THE VCTK DATASET, IN 100 EPOCHS

CNN models	Accuracy
DenseNet201	0.356
ResNet50_v2	0.350
Inception_v3	0.280
Xception	0.330

methodology. For this purpose, we employed flattened spectrograms as input vectors to the CNNs and MLAs. The training, validation, and test sets were kept as shown in Table V.

We evaluated DenseNet [59], Inception [60], ResNet50 [61], and Xception [62]. These CNNs architectures were selected because they have been used in previous work related to audio processing [63], [64], [65] and also in image processing research [66], [67]. In Table VI, the results obtained can be seen.

On the other hand, among the classic MLAs, we assessed Support Vector Machine (SVM) [11], Gaussian Naive Bayes (GaussianNB) [68], Online Passive-Aggressive Classifier (PassiveAggressiveClassifier) [69], XGBoost (XGBClassifier) [70], K-Nearest Neighbors (KNeighborsClassifier) [71], Linear Discriminant Analysis (LinearDiscriminantAnalysis) [72] and Ridge (RidgeClassifierCV) [73]. For a preliminary selection of models, the training of the above-mentioned MLAs was carried out with the default hyperparameters, and the results are presented in Table VII.

Given the results presented in Table VI, the CNN selected to generate the heatmaps was a DenseNet pretrained with the flattened spectrograms of the training set from the VCTK dataset. Each spectrogram was processed by DenseNet, and 5 heatmaps were generated, one for each possible accent that DenseNet learned to classify.

The 3 MLAs, in Table VII, that obtained the highest accuracies using default hyperparameters were used for the experiment, these were SVM, Online Passive-Aggressive Classifier, and Gaussian Naive Bayes.

5) *Hyperparameter and scaling optimization*: In the complete methodology pipeline, hyperparameter optimization was performed using grid search.

TABLE VII

VALIDATION ACCURACY OF CLASSIC MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS APPLIED TO THE END-TO-END CLASSIFICATION OF ACCENTS ON A SUBSET OF THE VCTK DATASET.

MLA	Accuracy
SVM	0.432
GaussianNB	0.414
PassiveAggressiveClassifier	0.391
XGBClassifier	0.362
KNeighborsClassifier	0.336
LinearDiscriminantAnalysis	0.388
RidgeClassifierCV	0.346

The hyperparameters used for SVM include: C in the range $[0.1, 1.0, 10]$, $kernel$ [linear, poly, rbf, sigmoid] and $degree$ $[0, 1, 2, 3]$. Where, C represents the regularization parameter, the strength of the regularization is inversely proportional to C . $kernel$ specifies the type of kernel to be used in the algorithm, and $degree$ the degree of the polynomial kernel function, used only if the kernel is “poly”.

Meanwhile, the hyperparameters tested for the Online Passive-Aggressive Classifier include: the possible values for max_iter are $[200, 500, 1000, 2000]$, and for tol $[10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-1}]$. Where, max_iter is the maximum number of epoch on the training data, and tol , the stop criterion. Iterations will stop when $loss > previous_loss - tol$.

In the case of Gaussian Naive Bayes, there are no optimizable hyperparameters.

On the other hand, spectrograms and Grad-Transfer feature descriptors have different value scales, so the selection of the scaling method directly influences the quality of the results achieved. For this reason, the following scalers were tested, as a new hyperparameter to be optimized by grid search together with the hyperparameters corresponding to each MLA. The scalers tested were the following:

- *Normalizer*: Normalize samples individually to unit norm.
- *MaxAbsScaler*: Scale each feature by its maximum absolute value.
- *PowerTransformer_yeo*: Apply a power transform featurewise to make data more Gaussian-like. The power transform implemented uses the Yeo-Johnson

method [74] which supports both positive and negative data.

- *StandarScaler*: Standardize features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance.

Therefore, for the optimization of hyperparameters, 84 SVMs were trained with each combination of hyperparameters and scaling methods fed by spectrograms and 84 SVMs fed by the proposed feature vectors. Likewise, 80 PassiveAggressiveClassifier were trained with spectrograms and 80 with the proposed feature vectors, and finally, 4 GaussianNB were trained with spectrograms and 4 GaussianNB with the proposed feature vectors.

The selection of the best set of hyperparameters was performed by training the models with the training set and evaluating them with the validation set. Once the best set of hyperparameters was selected, the resulting model was evaluated in the test set.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to establish a baseline to compare to, on the one hand, MLAs were fed with the original flatten spectrograms, which is the baseline and, on the other hand, they were fed with the original flatten spectrograms concatenated with the Grad-Transfer feature descriptors, after scaling, which constitutes the proposed feature vector. The three best MLAs proposed in Section IV-B4 were considered for evaluation of the methodology. We achieved the results presented in Table VIII.

As it can be observed, the highest accuracy in the test set among all models tested was 0.290 and it was obtained with a GaussianNB trained with the proposed feature vectors, representing an improvement of 7.46% with respect to the model trained with spectrograms (baseline). The scaling method that produced this result was the Normalizer. At the same time, a 7.3% improvement in the validation accuracy can be observed when comparing the best GaussianNB fed with the proposed feature vectors, with respect to the best GaussianNB trained with spectrograms.

The MLA that obtained the second-best results was the Passive-Aggressive Classifier which obtained a 7.3% performance improvement with respect to the reference descriptors in the test set, and a 1.6% improvement with the validation set. In this case the hyperparameters of Grad-Transfer approach were MaxAbsScaler as the scaling method, 500 *max_iter*, and 0.1 *tol*.

In last place, SVM, for which the Grad-Transfer approach achieved an improvement of 7.0% with respect to the model trained with spectrograms. Also, an improvement of 4.5% was achieved in the validation accuracy. In this case, the hyperparameters were Power Transformer with YeJohnson as the scaling method, C equal to 0.1, and a sigmoid kernel.

In the following, we present a brief analysis of the accuracy per class that we achieved using GaussianNB. The accuracy obtained per class was: Scottish 0.84, Canadian 0.32, American 0.25, British 0.03, and Irish 0.01. It can be observed that the Scottish accent has a remarkable performance above 80%, while the accents that the model has more difficulty classifying

are Irish and British. Good results may be due to the unique peculiarities of the accents whereas lower performances might be caused by accents that share similarities which would make the classification task more difficult for the model.

In all cases, it can be seen that the Grad-Transfer approach outperforms the results yielded by the baseline methods.

The results obtained show that the information extracted by the Grad-Transfer descriptor can be used by the classical machine learning models to increase their performance, absorbing part of the knowledge acquired by a CNN, which is expressed in the Grad-CAMs through the shape, position, and color of the heatmaps.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a new descriptor, which we called Grad-Transfer, for feature extraction in audio signals based on the use of the CNN-based class-discriminative localization technique Grad-CAM. We employed the Grad-Transfer features in the task of accent classification of native English speakers and tested the performance achieved by transferring the knowledge acquired in the training of the CNNs to other machine learning algorithms.

Preliminary experiments to test Grad-Transfer effectiveness in accent classification revealed that two clustering algorithms, *k*-means and Birch, generated clusters according to the original Grad-Transfer accents.

The results that we achieved on the VCTK dataset are higher than the baselines approaches that only use spectrograms (test accuracy improvement up to 7.46% with Gaussian Naive Bayes) and demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method. In addition, an improvement in the validation accuracy of each one of the models evaluated (SVM, Gaussian Naive Bayes, and Online Passive-Aggressive) for the optimization of hyperparameters was observed, reaching an improvement of 7.25% with Gaussian Naive Bayes.

Thus, it is demonstrated that, through Grad-Transfer, it is possible to improve the results achieved by the machine learning algorithms specialized in the classification of accents. Furthermore, the results obtained imply that the proposed method represents the first approach to knowledge transfer from a CNN to a different model of machine learning, by means of Grad-CAM, in the audio processing field.

The proposed method can be applied to other audio processing tasks since the premise of Grad-Transfer is to take advantage of the regions of the spectrograms (defined in terms of time and frequency) derived from the localization maps that are important to predict an audio category.

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TABLE VIII

THE ACCURACIES ACHIEVED ON A SUBSET OF THE VCTK DATASET BY FLATTENED SPECTROGRAMS (BASELINE) AND FLATTENED SPECTROGRAMS CONCATENATED WITH THE GRAD-TRANSFER FEATURE DESCRIPTORS (OURS).

MLA	Baseline		Ours	
	Val acc.	Test acc.	Val acc.	Test acc.
SVM	0.469	0.242	0.490	0.259
PassiveAggressive	0.431	0.246	0.438	0.264
GaussianNB	0.414	0.268	0.444	0.288

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